

Recovery of Potassium Iodide from Liquors Left after Iodometric Estimation of Copper

M. K. Bose

One of the commercial methods of preparation of potassium iodide is thermal reduction of solid potassium iodate usually in presence of carbon¹. In another method², an alkali thiosulphate is used in the reaction between iodine and alkali to prevent formation of iodate. Neutral iodates are also reduced to iodides by Devadar's alloy although zinc or aluminium alone is not suitable³.

It has been observed that in a hot neutral solution, iron filings can be effectively employed to reduce iodates to iodides; a trace of free iodine in the solution seems greatly to facilitate reduction, probably due to formation of hydroiodic acid by hydrolysis of ferrous iodide. It has been observed further that the iodine of the insoluble cuprous iodide can be completely converted into soluble ferrous iodide when stirred with iron filings. Based on the above observations, the following method has been developed for the recovery of potassium iodide from liquors left after iodometry of copper.

Procedure.—Cuprous iodide, separated from the solution and made into a uniform slurry with hot water, was slowly added to an excess of iron filings (60 mesh) under mechanical stirring when a vigorous reaction ensued. After boiling and stirring for a few minutes more, the solution containing ferrous iodide was filtered, the filtrate and washings were mixed with the main solution.

The solution (12 litres, 1-3% approx.), contained in a narrow-mouthed bottle provided with stopper and inlet and outlet tubes, was acidified with H_2SO_4 (d 1.8, 100 ml). Sodium nitrite solution (200 ml, 40%) was pushed in, a little at a time, by means of oxygen from a cylinder and discharged at the bottom of the solution in the bottle through the inlet tube and a pressure of oxygen was also maintained inside the bottle. Precipitation of iodine was complete within a few minutes when oxygen was turned off. The solution was allowed to settle. The solid iodine was separated from the solution and distilled in steam.

A hot and strong solution of KOH (ca. 20%) was gradually added to iodine, suspended in water, till the solution became colorless. It was then diluted, boiled, and small quantities of iodine were slowly added to the boiling solution until a distinct brown colour of iodine persisted. Iron filings (60 mesh) were added gradually in excess to the boiling solution under mechanical stirring. Reduction was complete in about

1. Thorpe, "Dictionary of Applied Chemistry".
2. Martin, "Industrial Chemistry".
3. Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", Vol. I.

45 minutes and the solution ceased to show colour with starch when acidified. After filtration and washing, the solution was neutralised with potassium carbonate, filtered, washed, and evaporated when crystals of potassium iodide separated.

The crude salt assays 96-97% potassium iodide and is free from iron and oxidising substances. The yield varied between 80 and 90% of potassium iodide used in titrations of copper.

The author's thanks are due to Shri A.A.J. Gomez, Master of the Mint, Bombay, for his interest in this piece of investigation and for his permission to publish the work.

ASSAY DEPARTMENT
INDIA GOVERNMENT MINT,
BOMBAY.

Received May 6, 1964.